

The 1st Forum of the Academy of Medical Sciences of the Serbian Medical Society

The Academy of Medical Sciences of the Serbian Medical Society (Academy) gathers our most famous scientists and experts from various fields of medicine and dentistry. During the 46 years of its activity, the Academy has held over 850 scientific and educational meetings, a large number of lecture cycles for the general population at the Ilija M. Kolarac Endowment, it has published dozens of monographs and thus contributed to the promotion of the scientific and professional work of distinguished members of the Academy, as well as to the education of doctors and the popularization of science.

On March 24, 2023, the Academy will organize the *1st Forum of the Academy of Medical Sciences of the Serbian Medical Society*. It will be a scientific meeting where the research results of the members of the Academy and their coworkers will be presented and discussed with the aim of promoting their scientific work and realizing their better cooperation in subsequent studies. The topic of the *1st Forum of the Academy* is "Prevention, Diagnosis, Treatment and Control of Mass Infectious and Non-Infectious Diseases." It has been our opinion that such a broad topic would attract experts from various fields and thus illustrate the wide-ranging field of scientific interest and work of the Academy members.

Twenty-four papers have been submitted for the *1st Forum of the Academy*. The greatest attention is paid to COVID-19. The results and experiences of the clinical presentation, course, treatment, and outcome of the disease are presented, as well as the results of experimental research and presentations of various post-COVID disorders. These results and experiences are valuable guideposts for planning measures in future epidemics that infectologists and epidemiologists have been warning us about.

In addition to COVID-19, lectures will also be delivered on some important infectious diseases that are not given enough attention, and which can seriously threaten health and life. These are, above all, tuberculosis and fungal diseases, which will be discussed by our well-known experts.

The meeting dedicated to mass diseases could not but include lectures on malignant diseases. Significant results of the study of modern drugs will be presented, as well as research of insufficiently studied tumors that require additional education of doctors, especially concerning the diagnosis of these diseases.

At the Forum, there will be an opportunity to find out the results of clinical and experimental studies on cardiovascular diseases, such as pharmacogenetic studies and analyses of the results of modern methods of cardiovascular diseases treatment.

Studies from the field of dentistry confirm that modern research requires a multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary approach, which has made it possible to achieve exceptional progress in the treatment of oral and dental diseases.

In addition to the presentation from the aforementioned fields, results from ophthalmology, anesthesiology, and otorhinolaryngology will also be presented. The wide range of topics and the quality of submitted abstracts confirm that Academy members contribute significantly to professional and scientific work and the continuous progress of all fields of medicine.

We hope that at the *1st Forum of the Academy*, doctors from different specialties, as well as experts from other related fields, will gather and that a lively discussion will contribute to the quality of the meeting. We wish to all the participants that the Forum fulfills the expectations of us all – the organizers, the authors of the presented studies, and the audience – and that it will be an incentive for the Academy Forum to become a regular annual scientific meeting of the Academy.

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Development of the TAVR program at the Institute for Cardiovascular Diseases of Vojvodina

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Introduction/Objective Aortic stenosis is the most common valvular heart disease in elderly patients. In patients with high risk for surgical aortic valve replacement, TAVR (transcatheter aortic valve replacement) is method of choice. Since its introduction in 2002, the number of TAVR has been growing exponentially. We present the results of the TAVR program at the Institute for Cardiovascular Diseases of Vojvodina.

Methods During 2022, the procedure was performed in 23 patients with symptomatic severe aortic stenosis and high risk for surgical aortic valve replacement. The decision to perform the TAVR procedure was made by the TAVI team.

Results Mean age of the patients was 75.6 years and 57% of patients were men. Medtronic Evolut R valve was implanted in 16 patients (69.5%), the Abbott Portico valve in 7 patients (30.5%). Direct valve implantation was performed in 56.5% of patients. Valve predilatation was performed in 43.5% of patients, while valve postdilatation in 17.4% of patients. In all patients, the procedure was performed through a transfemoral access. Ultrasound-guided puncture was performed in 65.2% of patients, and in 34.8% of patients it was guided by angio-guidewire-ultrasound. Aortic regurgitation was not registered in 52.6% of patients, and mild aortic regurgitation was registered in 47.4% of patients. The average peak to peak gradient is 7 mmHg. The mean value of maxPg was 16.8 mmHg. In one patient, a pacemaker was implanted after the procedure. Vascular complications were noted in 11.8% of patients.

Conclusion Results indicate a low percentage of complications with favorable outcome in patients treated with the TAVR procedure.

Keywords: aortic stenosis; TAVI; transfemoral access

Conflict of interest: None declared.

Effects of metformin and its combinations with other repurposed drugs on fibrosarcoma in hamsters

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Introduction/Objective Many drugs registered for various other indications can act selectively on tumor receptors, signaling pathways, metabolic processes, bioenergetic factors, enzymes, proteins and genes that regulate proliferation, apoptosis and neoangiogenesis of the tumor without affecting these activities in healthy cells. The introduction of new drugs is a very long, complex and expensive process of research. Detecting an anticancer effect in drugs already registered for other indications and forming combinations, may directly reduce the time and cost of such research.

Methods The anticancer efficacy of metformin and its combinations with caffeine, itraconazole, nitroglycerin and mebendazole was tested on fibrosarcoma experimentally induced by BHK21/C13 cells in Syrian golden hamsters (6 animals per group, randomly allocated to control and experimental groups, doses equivalent to usual human doses). After animal sacrifice, tumors were excised and their size, biophysical characteristics, histology and immunohistochemistry were assessed. Blood samples were collected for hematological and biochemical analyses and the main organs were toxicologically analyzed. Statistical significance was determined by one-way ANOVA followed by the Student-Newman-Keuls post hoc test.

Results Only two-drug combinations of metformin with caffeine or itraconazole or nitroglycerin showed significant antitumor effects on hamster fibrosarcoma compared to control, regarding all tested tumor parameters ($P < 0.05$) without toxicity.

Conclusion Administration of metformin in combination with caffeine or itraconazole or nitroglycerin might be an effective and safe approach in novel nontoxic adjuvant anticancer treatment.

Keywords: metformin; caffeine; itraconazole; nitroglycerin; hamsters; fibrosarcoma

Conflict of interest: None declared.

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Experimental evaluation of the effects of anticancer modulation therapy on MAPK/PI3K/AKT/mTOR/NF- κ B signaling with non-toxic drugs

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Introduction/Objective The large diversity in molecular mechanisms of cancer regulation allows some marketed pleiotropic non-oncological non-toxic pharmaceuticals to be used in oncology, which may reduce the duration and cost of research on novel anticancer treatment. At present, there are no published results *in vivo* on the anticancer effects of certain combinations of non-oncological pleiotropic drugs (disulfiram, diclofenac, nitroglycerin, metformin, deoxycholic acid, mebendazole) that influence MAPK/PI3K/AKT/mTOR/NF- κ B signaling.

Methods The anticancer effects of the aforementioned repurposed drug combinations at 20-50% LD₅₀ (equivalent to the usual human dose) were assessed by fibrosarcoma growth kinetics (measured daily *in vivo* with calipers) and tumor apoptosis markers (COX4, cytochrome C) in hamsters, randomly allocated to control and experimental groups (6 animals per group). The animals were sacrificed 15-18 days after BHK-21/C13 tumor inoculation. Tumors were excised, measured and blood collected. Biophysical, pathohistological, toxicological, hematological, biochemical and statistical analyses were performed.

Results Disulfiram with metformin, disulfiram with deoxycholic acid and deoxycholic acid with metformin were combinations that showed significant antitumor effects on fibrosarcoma growth kinetics and tumor apoptosis markers in hamsters ($P < 0.05$). All examined drugs in efficacious combinations could inhibit MAPK/PI3K/AKT/mTOR/NF- κ B signaling. Addition of the NF- κ B stimulator, mebendazole, to effective two-drug combinations rescued cancer growth, indicating that these pathways may be responsible for the antitumor action.

Conclusion The combinations of non-oncological drugs: disulfiram with metformin, disulfiram with deoxycholic acid and deoxycholic acid with metformin have the potential to be used as effective non-toxic adjuvant anticancer therapy in oncology.

Keywords: disulfiram; deoxycholic acid; metformin; hamsters; BHK-21/C13; fibrosarcoma; signal pathway

Conflict of interest: None declared.

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